

Aerodynamics of bobsleighs

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1 Introduction

Bobsleigh is a winter sport that combines technique, speed and strategy and was first included in the Olympic Games in 1924. The sport is performed on icy tracks, where athletes descend in the shortest time possible in a streamlined vehicle known as a bob. Bobsleigh events are categorised according to the number of participants in the bob. This study focuses on the descent phase of the women’s monobob, a new discipline included in the Winter Olympics in 2022, specifically in the context of the La Plagne Olympic track, that will be used for the 2030 Winter Games.

A bobsleigh race consists of two distinct phases. The first is the push phase, during which athletes propel the bob over a short distance to achieve maximum initial speed. This phase lasts approximately 7 seconds, during which the bob covers a distance of 40 meters, reaching a speed of 30 km/h at the end. The second phase is the descent, which lasts about 60 seconds and covers a distance of 1500 meters. During this phase, speeds of up to 130 km/h are reached. Performance in the descent is influenced by several factors, including the aerodynamics of the bob, the characteristics of the track, and the pilot’s ability to navigate the course effectively.

Figure 1: Push phase (a) and descent phase (b) of a bobsleigh race

To examine this, we employ a dual approach. First, we develop a numerical simulation in OpenFOAM using data from wind tunnel tests to model the aerodynamics of the bob. Second, we analyse the unique characteristics of the Olympic track in La Plagne. Finally, we will discuss how these two analyses can be combined.

2 Aerodynamics of monobobs

In this section, we take a look at the monobob of the French bobsleigh team, piloted by Margot Boch. She participated in the wind tunnel tests and can be seen in the 3D scan of the monobob.

2.1 Wind tunnel measurements

In June 2024, measurements were carried out in the S4 wind tunnel at the Institut Aérotechnique. This wind tunnel is equipped with a test section with the following dimensions: $L = 10$ m, $l = 3$ m, and $h = 5$ m. The monobob and the athlete were placed on a plate, under which a force sensor was located to measure the drag and lift forces. Multiple measurements were taken at different wind speeds. The experimental setup is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Experimental setup of the S4 wind tunnel

Underneath the plate, with a surface area of approximately 10 m^2 , there is an air space at ambient pressure. This results in significant drag and lift forces, even in the absence of any load on the support. For this reason, the drag and lift forces of the empty support were measured in order to adjust the measurements taken with the monobob and the athlete.

The measured forces for the empty support, together with quadratic regressions of the form $y(v) = av^2$, are given in Figure 3. The coefficients obtained for these adjustments are summarised in Table 1.

Figure 3: Aerodynamic forces (a) and errors (b) for these forces for the bobsleigh support

Forces	Coefficient a
F_X	$1.6180 \cdot 10^{-3}$
F_Z	$2.0999 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Err_{F_X}	$6.6134 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Err_{F_Z}	$1.2118 \cdot 10^{-4}$

Table 1: Coefficients associated with the forces F_X and F_Z , together with their errors.

The values $F_{\text{corrected}}$ are obtained using Equation 2.1.

$$F_{\text{corrected}}(v) = F_{\text{raw}}(v) - a \cdot v^2 \quad (2.1)$$

For the monobob, the experimental data are summarized in Table 2.

Air velocity (km/h)	Drag _{corrected} (N) Value	Drag _{raw} (N) Value	Lift _{corrected} (N) Value \pm Error	Lift _{raw} (N) Value \pm Error
50.0	10.4 ± 2.0	14.4 ± 1.5	3.0 ± 1.3	4.6 ± 1.0
70.1	20.7 ± 3.5	28.6 ± 2.5	9.7 ± 2.5	13.0 ± 1.9
90.0	34.7 ± 6.1	47.8 ± 4.4	14.6 ± 3.3	20.0 ± 2.3
101.6	44.3 ± 7.5	61.0 ± 5.3	21.4 ± 4.4	28.2 ± 3.1
110.9	52.9 ± 9.1	72.8 ± 6.5	19.5 ± 4.7	27.6 ± 3.3

Table 2: Corrected and raw drag and lift force measurements with corresponding errors at different air speeds.

2.2 CFD simulation

In parallel with the wind tunnel tests, a 3D scan of the bobsleigh with the athlete was carried out at the Institut Aérotechnique. This scan is shown in Figure 4a. The simulation

domain is a rectangular volume with the dimensions $40\text{ m} \times 10\text{ m} \times 10\text{ m}$, generated using blockMesh. The front of the monobob is positioned 10 m from the inlet. The mesh was generated using snappyHexMesh, as shown in Figure 4b. Around the bobsleigh, the characteristic mesh size was set to $5 \cdot 10^{-3}\text{ m}$.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: Visualisation of the 3D scan (a) and cross-sectional view of the monobob mesh (b)

After several trials, the "Spalart-Allmaras Delayed Detached Eddy Simulation" model was selected over the $k - \omega$ model. Indeed, with the $k - \omega$ model, the calculated lift was negative, contrary to the experimental measurements, whereas the Spalart-Allmaras model produced a positive lift consistent with the experiments. We assume that the better results obtained with this model are due to its ability to accurately capture separated flows, which frequently occur around the bobsleigh due to its lack of aerodynamic optimisation at the rear, as illustrated in Figure 5a.

In terms of numerical schemes, highly convergent parameters were chosen. The simu-

lation was carried out over a duration of 0.15 s, with a time step of 10^{-4} s using `pisoFoam`. The study focused on aerodynamic pressure forces, as viscous forces were negligible in comparison [RS18].

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: Velocity field (a) and relative pressure field (b) around the monobob after 0.15 seconds of simulation for an air speed of 100 km/h

In addition to velocity fields, the simulation allowed for the calculation of the relative pressure field. Using `paraView`, the numerical drag and lift were determined by integrating the relative pressure over the bobsleigh surface, weighted by the x or z components of the surface normals, respectively, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Relative pressure on the bobsleigh surface, weighted by the x (right) or z (left) components of the surface normals

2.3 Comparison of results

The numerical results obtained were compared to experimental values in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Experimental and numerical drag (a) and lift (b) of the monobob for various air speeds

In conclusion, the parameters chosen for the CFD simulation successfully reproduce the aerodynamic behavior of a monobob within the speed range observed on a track. Therefore, the numerical wind tunnel is validated and operational for this type of application.

3 Bobsleigh track at La Plagne

This study focuses on the bobsleigh track located in La Plagne, France. The track is 1500 meters long and has a vertical drop of 200 meters. It features 19 turns of varying radii and inclinations.

3.1 Path along the track

A 3D scan of the track was conducted by Institut National de l'Information Géographique et Forestière using photogrammetry. The resulting file, containing approximately 80 million points, is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Photogrammetry scan of the La Plagne track

To establish a path along the track, the course was also manually traversed. The measurement method involved starting 15 meters before the official start line and using a laser to measure successive points based on angular increments. This process continued until the track's endpoint, yielding a total of 1,600 recorded points. However, due to cumulative measurement errors, the resulting path deviates from the actual track, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Comparison between the initial path and the track scan

To create a corrected path that closely follows the track, a Python-based algorithm was developed. The algorithm processes the initial path by performing the following steps at each point:

- Select all 3D points from the track scan that lie within a bounding box with the dimensions $2\text{ m} \times 4\text{ m} \times 4\text{ m}$ centered on the current path point.
- Project the selected 3D points onto a plane orthogonal to the original path and passing through the current point.
- Compute the centroid of the projected points.
- Update the current path point to this centroid.
- Apply the same displacement vector to the subsequent points in the initial path.

The corrected path aligns closely with the actual track and is considered representative of the path taken by a bobsleigh. Projections of the corrected path onto different planes are shown in Figures 10, 11a, and 11b.

Figure 10: Bobsleigh path on the La Plagne track projected onto the XY plane

Figure 11: Bobsleigh path projections onto the XZ (a) and YZ (b) planes

The altitude of the path as a function of progress along the track is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Path altitude as a function of progress along the bobsleigh track in La Plagne

The curvature is defined by $\frac{|x'y''-y'x''|}{(x'^2+y'^2)^{3/2}}$ as a function of progress along the track. It is illustrated in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Curvature as a function of progress along the bobsleigh track in La Plagne

By analysing the curvature, the track can be divided into three sections: straight segments, small turns, and large turns, based on curvature thresholds. These categories are represented in Figure 14, and their proportions are detailed in Table 3.

Figure 14: Curvature along the track (a) and track path projected onto the XY plane (b) with categorisation of track sections into straight segments (green), small turns (blue), and large turns (red)

Track Section	Proportion (%)
Straight segment	49%
Small turn	20%
Large turn	31%

Table 3: Proportions of track sections on the La Plagne bobsleigh track

3.2 Data recording during the 2023 World Cup race

During the 2023 World Cup at La Plagne, data from Margot Boch’s race were recorded. Sensors installed on her bobsleigh, including a speed sensor and a positional tracker, provided speed and elapsed time data throughout the track. Margot Boch at the start of the race is shown in Figure 15, and the speed and time profiles are presented in Figure 16.

Figure 15: Margot Boch at the start of the 2023 Bobsleigh World Cup in La Plagne

Figure 16: Bobsleigh speed (a) and elapsed time (b) as a function of progress along the track

3.3 Monobob race analysis

By combining the track analysis with Margot Boch's race data, the percentage of time spent in straight segments, small turns, and large turns is shown in Figures 17, 18, and 19, respectively.

Figure 17: Percentage of time spent in straight segments as a function of speed

Figure 18: Percentage of time spent in small turns as a function of speed

Figure 19: Percentage of time spent in large turns as a function of speed

Athletes report that small turns are the most challenging to navigate. Consequently, attention should be focused on straight segments and large turns, where speeds are predominantly around 30 m/s, indicating a need for optimisation in this speed range.

4 Conclusion

This study investigated the aerodynamics of the monobob and its performance on the La Plagne bobsleigh track. Through a combination of wind tunnel measurements, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations, and track analysis, key insights into the aerodynamic behavior of the monobob were obtained.

The wind tunnel experiments provided a baseline for drag and lift forces at varying speeds. The CFD simulations validated these results, demonstrating the effectiveness of the Spalart-Allmaras model in capturing the complex flow phenomena, particularly the separated flows around the bobsleigh's rear. The agreement between experimental and numerical results confirms the robustness of the simulation setup for future aerodynamic studies.

The analysis of the La Plagne track divided it into straight sections, small turns, and large turns. Combining this track analysis with race data from Margot Boch's 2023 World Cup performance revealed that while small turns present the greatest challenge, the majority of time is spent in straight sections and large turns. This indicates the need to optimise monobob performance for speeds around 30 m/s, which dominate these sections.

The next step in this research will be to simulate the monobob using the Spalart-Allmaras model in a straight section and a large turn of the track at a speed of 30 km/h. Modifying the position or orientation of the bobsleigh during these simulations could help identify optimal trajectories within the track, further enhancing performance and providing valuable insights for race strategies.

Bibliography

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